

HARMFUL ALGAE NEWS

An IOC Newsletter on toxic algae and algal blooms

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No. 42

First records of *Ostreopsis heptagona*, *O. cf. siamensis* and *O. cf. ovata* – in the Azores archipelago, Portugal

During summer 2008, surveys were carried out around São Miguel island in the Azores archipelago (36–39°N, 25–31°W) (Fig. 1). The sampling area is located between the main paths of the Azores Current (AC) and North Atlantic Current. The average SST around the island, was above 21°C, denoting a greater influence of the AC. Seawater samples were collected with a Niskin bottle, and preserved with neutralized formalin, for phytoplankton observations and cell counting. Species of *Ostreopsis* were morphologically characterized with an Olympus BX50 equipped with

epifluorescence, following Penna *et al.* [1]. The three *Ostreopsis* species were found together in the water, exclusively on the north side of the island where the waters were warmer. The highest concentration of *Ostreopsis* spp. was 90 cells L⁻¹.

The measurements (Table 1) and plate patterns observed suggest the presence of three species of *Ostreopsis*: *O. heptagona* Norris, Bomber *et al.* (Fig. 2), *O. cf. siamensis* Schmidt, 1982 (Fig. 3) and *O. cf. ovata* Fukuyo, 1981 (Fig. 4).

Since sampling was not focussed on

Fig. 2. *O. heptagona*, LM, epithecal view (scale bar = 20 µm). The distinct feature of plate 5", pentagonal, in contact with 1", can be observed. (Cont'd on p.2)

First records of *Ostreopsis cf. siamensis* in Moroccan Atlantic upwelling waters

Fig. 1. *Ostreopsis cf. siamensis* from a sample off Cape Ghir. Light microscopy – phase contrast (a). Epitheca (b) and hypotheca (c) views. (right).

We report the first records of *Ostreopsis cf. siamensis* Schmidt detected in the NE Africa Atlantic upwelling system by the Moroccan HAB and phycotoxins national monitoring programme. The species was identified by phase contrast (Fig. 1) and epifluorescence microscopy during the Morocco-Portugal project of scientific cooperation on HABs and marine

biotoxins. Identification was confirmed by sequencing the 5.8S –ITS and LSU ribosomal genes [1].

Ostreopsis blooms were first observed in seawater samples from the Cape Ghir region (30°N, 9°W) on 5 October 2004, reaching 3.7 x 10³ cell L⁻¹. Blooms recurred in the following years, and increased in concentration and duration, reaching 9.8 x 10³ to

1.2 x 10⁴ cell L⁻¹ in 2008, and a maximum of 10⁵ cell L⁻¹ observed in August 2009. In 2007, *O. cf. siamensis* cells were observed from late summer to early autumn, in 2008 from early summer to late autumn, and in 2009 from spring to late autumn. The blooms occurred with surface temperatures ranging from 20 to 24°C, with maxima recorded in August and September. In parallel, the detection of toxins by mouse bioassay in mussels collected from the same area indicated the presence of neurotoxins.

Four monitoring stations were sampled in the Agadir area (Fig. 2). Highest *Ostreopsis* concentrations were always observed in samples from Cape Ghir and a station further north, at Tamri, both sites located on a rocky coastline highly exposed to northerly (upwelling favourable) winds and waves

(Cont'd on p. 3)

(Cont'd from p. 1)

Fig. 3. *O. cf. siamensis*, LM, epithelial (top) and hipotechal views (center) (scale bar = 20 μm).

Fig. 4. *O. cf. ovata*, LM, epithelial view (top) (scale bar = 10 μm).

Fig. 1. The Azores archipelago: São Miguel (oriental group).

Table 1. Dorsoventral and transversal measurements.

	Dorsoventral diameter (μm)	Transverse diameter (μm)
<i>O. heptagona</i> (Fig. 2)	80–83	53–55
<i>O. cf. siamensis</i> (Fig. 3)	60–70	34–42
<i>O. cf. ovata</i> (Fig. 4)	49–51	22–30

the study of this genus, the fixative used did not allow complementary phylogenetic analysis. Future research will comprise genotyping *Ostreopsis* strains by PCR based assay.

This preliminary work in Azores waters is expected to contribute to the biogeographical distribution of HAB species, and to clarify their role as environmental tracers in Atlantic waters and as climate indicators.

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See you in Hersonissos, Crete, in November!

(Cont'd from p. 1)

(Fig. 2). In contrast, other dinoflagellate species were favoured at stations south of Agadir, in the shadow of the Cape, on a sandy coast with calmer waters. This suggests that turbulent conditions north of the cape favoured resuspension of this epiphytic species in the water column although not dispersing the cells. Villa *et al.* [2] also pointed out that *Ostreopsis* sp. prefers more turbulent conditions than other benthic dinoflagellates such as *Coolia monotis*. In contrast, the abundance of *Ostreopsis ovata* in the Adriatic Sea was significantly higher in sheltered sites compared with exposed ones, indicating a major role of hydrodynamism in regulating bloom dynamics [3].

According to a recent study of the phylogeography of *Ostreopsis* species based on several strains isolated from the Mediterranean and Northeast Atlantic [1], *O. cf. siamensis* was, until now, only observed in the Mediterranean, while *O. cf. ovata* was found both in the Mediterranean and NE Atlantic, e.g. in Madeira and the Canary Islands. However, neither species was observed on the upwelling coasts of Iberia, such as the Galician *rias* (Santiago Fraga, pers. com.), or NW Africa where the species was not investigated before. Simultaneously, during the Morocco blooms, a strain of *O. cf. siamensis* was isolated from macroalgae off the SW coast of Portugal [4]. It is possible that this species is actually spreading in this region of the Atlantic due to an exchange between the Atlantic and the Mediterranean basins or even to a warming of these coastal upwelling waters [5]. However, it is not yet clear whether this apparent biogeographical expansion is real since HAB monitoring only became routine on the Agadir coast after 2002, and there is still no monitoring programme for microphytobenthic communities along the Moroccan coast. After these *Ostreopsis* blooms and due to their annual re-occurrence, the HAB monitoring programme has included this genus among the potentially harmful species of the Atlantic and Mediterranean coasts of Morocco.

Fig. 2. Location of Moroccan monitoring stations in Agadir region and photo of Cape Ghir (lower left) and Sidi Rbat (lower right) monitoring sites.

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Ostreopsis cf. *siamensis* proliferations in coastal water of Bizerte, Northern Tunisia

Fig. 1. Sampling stations in the Bizerte region.

As part of national monitoring network for bivalve molluscs and sea urchins for Northern Tunisia (Fig. 1), detection of potentially toxic microalgae, including *Ostreopsis* cf. *siamensis* (Fig. 2) were carried out in Lake Bizerte, a coastal lagoon. Sampling was also carried out on coasts of the Bizerte region. Lake Bizerte is the only mollusc culture site in Tunisia, with 6 farms producing mussels and oysters. The coastal waters of Bizerte support a sea urchin industry. Seawater was sampled weekly from Lake Bizerte near station B1, and every month at 4 coastal stations, B4, B5, B6 and B7 (Fig. 1). The samples were taken at the surface and at a depth of 5 m. Counting of *O. siamensis* was carried out after sedimentation.

From 2007 to 2009 and for the first time in Bizerte coastal waters, we recorded the dinoflagellate *Ostreopsis siamensis*. Maximum concentrations were found in July 2007 (3.75×10^4 cells L^{-1}) as well as during August and November 2008 at stations B4 and B7 (Fig. 4).

Monitoring of plankton microalgae was carried out between 2004 and 2008 in Lake Bizerte at station B1 where maximum concentrations for *O. cf. siamensis* and *Coolia monotis* growing mainly as epiphytes or as part of the benthos, were about 24.7×10^4 and 17.5×10^3 cells L^{-1} in July 2006 and May

2008, respectively (Fig. 3).

The monitoring of phycotoxins in the flesh of urchins collected in the Bizerte region (B4 to B7) allowed us to record contamination of these organisms by DSP-type toxins during the following periods: April–May 2007, early January and the beginning of March and August 2008 (Fig. 4).

Discussion

The morphology of the *Ostreopsis* cells suggests that there are two distinct species in the Mediterranean: *O. cf. siamensis* and *O. ovata* [1]. *Ostreopsis ovata* was first observed in the Mediterranean in 1972 at Villefranche-sur-Mer [2].

During the last 10 years, several blooms have been reported along the coast of Tuscany (northern Tyrrhenian

Fig. 2. Micrographs of the dinoflagellate *Ostreopsis siamensis*: Cells of *O. siamensis* (a), fixed in Lugol's, (b) epiphytic (c), hypotheca (d), detail of the antapex.

Fig. 3. Densities of the dinoflagellate *Ostreopsis siamensis* in Lake Bizerte at station B1.

Sea). They have been associated with mortalities of marine fauna [3]. The most probable period for blooming in this alga on the Tyrrhenian Sea coast (Province of Campania) is June and July [2]. Tognetto *et al.* [4] observed *Ostreopsis* in the Tyrrhenian Sea from August to October 2004 and found a link between the concentration of this alga and water temperature, with a maximum in August around 28°C.

In Tunisian waters, high concentrations of *O. siamensis* were recorded in *Posidonia* meadows in the Gulf of Tunis, with maxima of about 3.5×10^5 cells L⁻¹ from July to August [5] as well as in waters of the Gulf of Gabès, with a concentration around 300 cells L⁻¹ in October [6]. In the Northern Lake of Tunis, considerable growth of *C. monotis* was recorded in April 2005 following clearance of aquatic vegetation on the banks of the lake [7]. Maxima were around 5×10^5 cells L⁻¹ in the southern part of

the lake.

Ostreopsis produces palytoxins that, with ciguatoxins, are amongst the most toxic natural toxins known. Palytoxins occur in the Mediterranean taxa of both *O. cf. siamensis* and *O. ovata*.

At Genoa in 2005, following cases of human illness, water samples were taken from five beaches, every day for the first week, then twice a week, then once a week. The first samples showed maximum concentrations of *Ostreopsis* of 33,000 cells L⁻¹ in the water column, and 182,000 cells g⁻¹ on macrophytes [8].

The analyses of the water, plankton and macrophytes showed the presence of “putative” palytoxin, the term “putative” being used because the test can show positive for several isomers of palytoxin [9].

In Bari, southern Italy, in two separate events in 2003 and 2004, three days after recording the first symptoms, water samples were taken, in which *Ostreopsis* was found to be abundant,

with over 1 million cells L⁻¹ [10]. During the blooms, gastropods and crabs appeared unaffected (which does not mean that they did not accumulate toxin, but rather that they seemed not to be susceptible to it), while mussels, limpets and sea urchins seems markedly affected (many empty shells, and loss of spines) [11].

The presence of *Ostreopsis siamensis* in Mediterranean waters should be further investigated, integrating the water column, the sediments and vegetative cover. Such work will permit hypotheses to be proposed and tested about the dispersion and the introduction of phytoplankton species, and will help in understanding the causes of blooms. It will allow water-colonisation dynamics and processes to be better understood for the complex of invasive species. Projects targeting the ecology of toxic algae and the genetics of populations of the different species of *Ostreopsis* will help understanding of the causes of blooms on Mediterranean coasts.

Acknowledgements

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Fig. 4. Densities of the dinoflagellate *O. siamensis* in Lake Bizerte at stations B4 to B7 in the Bizerte region (☆: presence of DSP toxins in sea urchins. Source: DGSV, 2009).

First detection of *Ostreopsis cf. siamensis* in Portuguese coastal waters

The coast of Portugal is located in the warm temperate/sub-tropical biogeographical transition of the North Atlantic. It is part of the major discontinuity in the eastern boundary of the NE Atlantic, being affected both by seasonal upwelling and water mass exchange between the Mediterranean and Atlantic basins [1].

In October 2007, following repeated reports of nuisance blooms associated with *Ostreopsis* species in the Mediterranean Sea (www.bentoxnet.it), a sampling programme aimed at early detection of *Ostreopsis* species along the Portuguese coast was initiated. The first survey targeted coastal lagoons along the south coast (Ria Formosa and Alvor), under influence of the Mediterranean outflow and where the environmental conditions are more likely to favour the development of dinoflagellate assemblages with warm-temperate to tropical affinities (Fig. 1). The survey was repeated in July 2008. Samples were collected by harvesting macroalgae, such as *Dictyota dichotoma* (Phaeophyceae), *Codium decorticatum* and *Ulva rigida* (Chlorophyta) and mixed microalgae mats attached to pontoons and other surfaces, eel grass and floating organic debris. Plankton net tows (20 μ m) were also collected. From 2008 onwards, 2 recreational marinas on the west coast were sampled (Fig. 1). Samples were collected from floating pontoons, at depths never deeper than arms' length, by detaching macroalgae from pontoon

walls and buoys. Prior to analysis samples were kept in plastic flasks with seawater from the collection site and transported to the laboratory under cool conditions.

Samples were vigorously shaken and the water poured into plastic Petri-dishes to be checked under an inverted microscope (Olympus IX70). Single cells of *Ostreopsis* sp. were isolated by micropipette and transferred to culture wells with filter-sterilized seawater from the sampling site. When cell numbers were observed to consistently increase, cells were transferred to f/50-Si medium (35 psu) and finally to f/20-Si medium (35 psu), where they were routinely maintained. Cultures were kept at $19^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ with overhead illumination of $40 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, supplied with cool white fluorescent lamps, and a light:dark cycle of 14:10 (L:D).

From all the samples analysed, specimens attributable to *Ostreopsis* were only detected in Sines marina ($37^{\circ} 57' 2 \text{ N}$; $8^{\circ} 51' 53 \text{ W}$) (June 2008, October 2008 and September 2009). On June 2008, the species was associated with *Colpomenia peregrina* (Phaeophyceae). Three cultures were established and are now kept in the culture collection of the Oceanography Centre, University of Lisbon (ALISU strains IO96-01, IO96-02 and IO96-03). Strain IO96-02 was analysed for species-specific genotyping. Approximately 10 mL of exponentially growing culture were harvested by centrifugation (4000 rpm, 5 min). The

Fig. 1. Location of sampling stations (arrows) with indication of site where *Ostreopsis cf. siamensis* was identified (star).

pelleted cells were rinsed twice with filter sterilized (0.22 μ m) artificial seawater. Total genomic DNA was extracted as described in [2]. PCR amplification on the 5.8S rDNA and ITS regions and direct sequence reactions were conducted as described in [3]. The 5.8S rDNA-ITS sequences obtained in this study were aligned in BLAST silico platform and using the confidential ribosomal sequence database at the Department of Biomolecular Sciences, University of Urbino.

The morphological analysis of isolated cells and cultures was done under the light microscope, using bright field and epifluorescence after staining with Calcofluor White [4], and by SEM (JEOL JSM-5200LV) (Fig. 2). The cells

Fig. 2. *Ostreopsis cf. siamensis*. Specimen from field sample attached by the ventral pore to particles in apical/antapical view (a) and in lateral view (b). Epithelial view of cultured specimen (SEM) (c).

analysed have the characteristic morphology and plate formula of *Ostreopsis* (Fig. 2). Cells are oval, markedly anteroposteriorly compressed, attaching to surfaces by the ventral pore (Fig. 2a and b). The morphological characteristics agree well with the description of *Ostreopsis siamensis* by [5] and *Ostreopsis* cf. *siamensis* by [2]. The wall is smooth covered with scattered pores of only one type (Fig. 2c). The dorso-ventral diameter varied between 58–61.2 μm ($n=12$) (61.2 μm in field specimen) and the width between 48–50 μm ($n=12$) (48.9 μm in field specimen). In side view, the cells did not show any evident undulation. When grown in f/2 medium, cells showed gross malformations and were difficult to interpret.

The final alignment of the ribosomal sequence of the tested *Ostreopsis* strain IO96-02 with all ribosomal sequences of *Ostreopsis* species available in the database used in this study revealed total identity (100%) with *O.* cf. *siamensis* sequences belonging to the Mediterranean clade [2]. Because of the lack of molecular data associated with strains from the type locality, we follow the recommendations of [6], and the species name we assign to the strain isolated from the Atlantic coast of Portugal is *Ostreopsis* cf. *siamensis*.

These results extend the geographical distribution of *O.* cf. *siamensis* outside the Mediterranean basin to 38° N, representing the highest latitude at which species of *Ostreopsis* have been reported from the Atlantic. For marine protists with no fossil record it is very difficult to assess whether

previously unreported species are native cryptogenic species that have been overlooked or the result of a recent introduction. Species of the genus *Ostreopsis*, although occasionally reported from the water column, are more commonly described as benthic-epiphytic [7]. Methods used in phytoplankton surveys do not aim at sampling benthic communities and these will only be detected on rare occasions when blooms develop or cells are re-suspended. Previous results on the phylogeny of *O. ovata* recognised several geographical clades and identified the temperate-tropical Atlantic and the Mediterranean basin as a single geographical unit [6]. The total identity of the analysed sequences from the Atlantic strain of *O.* cf. *siamensis* with the Mediterranean strains reported in the present study suggests a similar phylogeographical unit for *O.* cf. *siamensis*. Further studies on the phylogeography of this species based on more regional strains and other global populations will be needed to clarify the phylogenetic and phylogeographic position of *O.* cf. *siamensis* in Atlantic waters.

So far populations of *O.* cf. *siamensis* have not been detected in high numbers in Portuguese waters, nor have toxic events been reported. The site of Sines marina represents an artificial sheltered environment on an otherwise highly hydrodynamic coast influenced by seasonal upwelling. The geographical distribution of *Ostreopsis* spp. is generally associated with low energy systems and described as inter tropical and from warm waters, as in the

Mediterranean Sea [6–7]. However, the recent report of planktonic blooms of *O.* cf. *siamensis* along the upwelling coast of Morocco [8] should be considered as an early warning, and highlights the need for more studies on the distribution and ecology of *O.* cf. *siamensis* along the Portuguese coast.

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EFSA scientific opinions on marine biotoxins

In July 2006, the European Commission asked the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) to provide a scientific opinion to assess the current European Union (EU) limits with regard to human health and methods of analysis for marine biotoxins as established in the EU legislation, including new emerging toxins.

From that moment until now, EFSA's Panel on Contaminants in the Food Chain (CONTAM Panel) has

developed and adopted a series of scientific opinions related to marine biotoxins: **okadaic acid** (OA) and analogues (2008), **azaspiracid** (AZA)-group toxins (2008), **yessotoxin** (YTX)-group toxins (2008), influence of processing on the levels of **lipophilic** marine biotoxins in bivalve molluscs (2008), **saxitoxin** (STX)-group toxins (2009), **pectenotoxin** (PTX)-group toxins (2009), **domoic acid** (DA) (2009), summary on **regulated marine**

biotoxins (2009), **palytoxin** (PITX)-group toxins (2009), **ciguatoxin** (CTX)-group toxins (2010), **cyclic imines** (CIs) (spiroptides, gymnodimines, pinnatoxins and pteriatoxins) (2010), and **brevetoxin** (BTX)-group toxins (2010), and also the most recent statement on **shellfish consumption figure** (2010).

All these reports have been printed in the EFSA Journal and are available on-line at: www.efsa.europa.eu/en/panels/contam.htm

Beyond Guam: Current status of research on the neurotoxic amino acid BMAA by cyanobacteria

The production of toxins by cyanobacteria is well documented, and new compounds continue to be isolated and described. Observations on and reports from the Island of Guam in the 1940's and 1950's described an increased incidence of a neurodegenerative disease among the Chamorro people there. This disease termed *lytico-bodig* by the indigenous people was described as an Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis-Parkinsonism Dementia Complex (ALS-PDC) with an incidence 50-100 times greater than the world average. Research concerning possible causes and mechanisms has been ongoing and the only statistical correlate identified with the disease was diet [1].

Studies on Guam isolated a number of toxic compounds from cycads, including a novel neurotoxic amino acid $\hat{\alpha}$ -N-methylamino-L-alanine (BMAA). Since that time investigators have examined the occurrence of this neurotoxin, from its initial isolation from cycads through to the potential occurrence of this compound worldwide. Even though BMAA has been studied for over 40 years, new insights and discoveries are still being made. In order to summarise the current status of the research on BMAA in cyanobacteria and its association with human disease, a special supplement of the journal *Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis* (November 2009, vol. 10, supplement 2) was recently devoted to this topic.

The supplement contains 20 contributions from environmental scientists, analytical chemists, neurologists and ethnobotanists. The supplement begins with a contribution from **Walter Bradley** and **Deborah Mash** outlining the cyanobacterial/BMAA hypothesis with its various strengths and weaknesses. The late Arthur Bell then provides a discussion on the discovery of BMAA, with examples of protein incorporation and biomagnification. **Peter Nunn**, one of **Arthur Bell**'s colleagues examines various phases of BMAA research,

considering the acute neurotoxicity of BMAA in experimental animals, followed by acute neurotoxicity in primates with a final discussion of the broader impacts of BMAA in toxicology.

Three submissions to the supplement consider human dietary exposure to BMAA. The first considers the diet of the Chamorro people, BMAA concentrations and the link with ALS-PDC (**Banack** and **Murch**). This is followed by an analysis of BMAA in cycad flour, a staple of the Chamorro diet, and underestimates due to a lack of analysis of protein-bound fractions (**Cheng** and **Banack**). Finally a new potential route of exposure to BMAA in the human diet is considered by **Roney et al.** They examined FaCai *Nostoc* soup, finding BMAA present within this foodstuff and not in fake FaCai made from starch.

Five papers consider the toxicity of BMAA following dietary exposure. **Vyas** and **Weiss** examine the toxicity of BMAA to motor neurons, which is followed by a contribution on the molecular mechanisms of BMAA neurotoxicity (**Lobner**). The remaining three papers consider the toxicity to invertebrates (*Drosophila*, **Zhou et al.**; *Artemia*, *Nassula*; **Purdie et al.**), *Danio rerio* (**Purdie et al.**) and avian vacuolar myelinopathy, a disease associated with epiphytic cyanobacteria on aquatic macrophytes (**Bidigare et al.**).

Human exposure to BMAA through the aquatic environment is then examined, with the need to monitor water resources (**Metcalf** and **Codd**), the use of HILIC-MS to monitor Dutch drinking waters (**Faassen et al.**) and cyanobacterial BMAA in the marine environment of South Florida (**Brand**). Small ponds and seeps in the Gobi Desert were also examined as these are water resources for the Gobi Bear, a critically endangered species and both BMAA and the related toxin 2,4-diaminobutyric acid (DAB) were identified in water resources where cyanobacteria were present (**Craighead et al.**). Researchers in New Hampshire have identified clusters of ALS patients

around lakes with cyanobacterial blooms and their current findings are also reported in the supplement (**Callier et al.**).

The incidence of ALS among veterans serving in the 1st Gulf War has increased compared to those not deployed [2]. Consequently, **Cox** and colleagues examine desert cyanobacterial crust and identify both DAB and BMAA in crust, and hypothesise that desert borne dust containing BMAA may have contributed to this increased incidence of disease. Finally, **Walter Bradley** discusses potential ALS therapies based on the BMAA/cyanobacteria hypothesis, and **Paul Cox** discusses the various tenets of the BMAA hypothesis. Submissions to this supplement are based on research presented at a special session of the 19th International Symposium on ALS/MND in Birmingham, UK in November 2008. As BMAA in cyanobacteria is currently a topic of great interest and concern, this supplement provides a definitive summary of the current state of this research.

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Patrick Gentien In Memoriam

Patrick was born in Saint Pol de Leon (Brittany, France) in 1950. He was a chemical engineer (HEI, Lille) and doctor of physical oceanography. His early professional days (1980-1982) started at the Australian Institute of Marine Science (AIMS). There with John Andrews, occasional upwellings on the central Great Barrier Reef were discovered (Andrews & Gentien 1982), a paradigm shift in the understanding of nutrient budgets for the reef. This finding has influenced reef research to this day. Patrick joined IFREMER in 1982 as a chemical researcher and hydrologist at the department of Coastal Environment and Marine Environmental Management. He joined a team tasked with making an ecological survey off Cap de Flamanville, where Electricité de France was building a nuclear power station. The survey lasted the three years (1983-1986) before the power station became operational. A dominant summer species in this region is *Karenia mikimotoi*, which became one of Patrick's lasting interests.

Karenia mikimotoi was first reported (as *Gyrodinium aureolum*) in European waters in 1966, and characteristically forms thin layers (another lasting interest) in the pycnocline as well as surface blooms. Vertical migrations of up to 15 m range take place when stratification is not too marked, but with increased stability, persistent non-migrating populations form in the pycnocline (the *magic carpet* of Bjoernsen & Nielsen 1991). Why? We don't know, but the question was one of many which challenged Patrick, and he often came up with ingenious explanations. Allelopathy exerted by *K. mikimotoi* may have been playing an effective role at the onset of the population development. An obvious problem facing cells which secrete toxins is how to protect themselves, whence the invocation of bioconvection cells ... by playing with the time scales of these convection cells, the secretion rate of the toxin, and its decay rate, Patrick argued that high concentrations of cells can exist without poisoning themselves. Ingenious, although how the toxin would then reach a sufficient

concentration to affect its intended target remains a mystery. Blooms of *Dinophysis* leading to massive and long-lasting shellfish harvesting closures due to diarrhetic shellfish toxins is another major problem in Brittany. As an engineer and expert on hydrodynamics, one of Patrick's passions was, in close cooperation with his colleague Michel Lunven, to develop appropriate high resolution instruments to hunt these cryptic, patchy and unpredictable creatures throughout the Bay of Biscay, and find their hiding place when they had apparently disappeared. Years later, and with the same (improved) equipment and colleagues Patrick performed multiple cruises in the Baltic Sea, Irish Sea, Galician Rías...and even in the Chilean fjords, always looking for fine resolution aggregates, thin layers of dinoflagellates, and the special hints that would explain the presence of a species bloom in a given place.

Beginning in the early 1990's, Patrick became deeply involved in international cooperation on harmful algal blooms research and management, while retaining his responsibilities at IFREMER. For the last 15 years he was the face of France at the ICES-IOC Working Group on HAB Dynamics (Chair 1996-1999), the Scientific Steering Committee of GEOHAB (Global Ecology and Oceanography of Harmful Algal Blooms IOC-SCOR, www.geohab.info) (founding Chair, 1999-2003) and the IOC Intergovernmental Panel on Harmful Algae Blooms. His unique way of species-specific targeted cruises and models was widely applied in diverse ecosystems and European projects, networks and others (*LIFEHAB*, *NEMEDA*, *HABIT*, and the forthcoming *ASIMOUTH*) often in cooperation with

US researchers.

Patrick passed away on Sunday 9 May. He had been fighting lung cancer for three months, but still his sudden death caught us all by surprise. Until the very end, he kept in touch with his projects and collaborators and continued

Photo Sonsoles González-Gil

work whenever the chemotherapy and accompanying exhaustion gave him a break. He leaves a wife, four children and two grandchildren. He was a key person in the establishment of links between HAB biologists and physical oceanographers and modellers. Those of us who worked with him had the opportunity to enjoy his sharp and acid sense of humour, his unique sense of criticism, and his always generous attitude to share original ideas and go to the core of scientific problems.

Here we present brief extracts from the numerous condolences we received from all over the world. The full texts written in their original languages (English, French, Spanish, Portuguese) will be posted on the ISSHA website (www.issaha.org).

Beatriz Reguera

Tim Wyatt

Appreciations

On est impressionné, admiratif sans doute, devant le courage et la volonté dont tu as fait preuve ces dernières semaines, toujours aux commandes, toujours plein d'idées, toujours débordant d'initiatives, et te préoccupant de la relève pour laquelle tu t'es battu, sans jamais évoquer ta maladie, évitant l'inutile, et programmant l'avenir (Pierre Le Hir, France)

Photo Mónica Lion

Dans le domaine des efflorescences microalgales Patrick s'est montré un visionnaire ... Toujours intéressé par la nouveauté, les découvertes dans tous les domaines l'ont passionné: depuis les performances instrumentales (avec Michel Lunven et Michel Lehaître: granulomètre laser utilisé dans de nombreuses mers, les échanges physicochimiques en zones stratifiées, ... les particularités de la viscosité... (avec toi Ian) ... Il faut également souligner le réalisme et le sens critique de Patrick, et sa sensibilité tant humaine qu'artistique. Tout ceci constituait un personnage attachant, auquel je pense encore parfois en me disant souvent: "je devrais en parler à Patrick", car j'oublie qu'il n'est plus (Geneviève Arzul, France)

entusiasmo contagioso ... me enseñó, con su mirada crítica a no tomar nada por sentado e ir despacio por el camino largo de las respuestas ... Patrick sabía reirse de si mismo y con los demás. Era capaz de sacarle

punta a un alfiler y le gustaban los juegos de palabras. No tenía pelos en la lengua y decía siempre lo que pensaba... una semana antes de su muerte... en sus ojos, la chispa de su genio y el afán de lucha seguían estando presentes. Para mi, Patrick sigue estando entre nosotros porque sus ideas y sus consejos no han muerto con él (Lourdes Velo, France)

Patrick was one of the most intellectually honest and insightful scientists I have been privileged to know. His spirit was generous, as were his practices... his wonderfully dry humor. Patrick's twinkling eyes were clear signals that he was engaged in an exchange that pleased, provoked and challenged everyone in the conversation. His enigmatic smile signaled he was already a step ahead of exchange and waiting for us around the turn (Pat Tester, USA)

Un gran sentido del humor el tuyo... recuerdo tus sonrisas y tus ojillos risueños entre la nube de tu cigarro... Ay, este humo, ... te fuiste con él, trabajando hasta el final... con esa actitud amigable que hace que la ciencia sea lo que debe ser ante todo: vocación y humanidad (Elisa Berdalet, Spain)

When we could just sit and chat we'd get all churned up with his excitement over thin layer sampling, somehow very infectious and challenging, with glasses of wine or other assorted liquids stimulating

Photo Mónica Lion

Photo Robin Raine

wild 'flights of fancy' over what we could learn from these new technologies. His quick joke or sly, slightly sarcastic quip with that smile and god-awful heavy cigarette smoke rising from his lips were all parts of our dialog (Kevin & Stella Sellner, USA)

He was a true scientist in that he never grew tired of asking questions. he was a great proponent of conducting HAB science within the "bigger picture" of mainstream phytoplankton ecology and oceanography (Grant Pitcher, South Africa)

Era também das pessoas com quem adorava conversar de ciência e de ir beber um copo e falar de música. Estava toda entusiasmada por irmos trabalhar em conjunto com ele pois era um excelente crítico para o nosso projecto com modeladores. Mas não largava o cigarro... Eu bem lhe dizia e ele punha sempre aquele sorrizinho malandro! (Teresa Moita, Portugal)

You have well described Patrick's character: a man of integrity, very generous and very willing to understand scientific questions, always helping and encouraging his co-workers (Michel Lunven, France)

We have lost one of the few who always cut through the BS and posturing in science—never afraid to point out when the "high-flyers" were over-stretching their science, and their own importance—always worth sharing ideas with, and very good company (Barrie Dale, Norway)

Un gran orientador científico... particle size analyzer... Lo hicimos funcionar a bordo del barquito Melipulli de la Universidad de Los Lagos, con grandes dificultades de habitabilidad, pero Patrick solo se reía y estaba tranquilo, pero a veces se enojaba un poquito, ya que se nos enredaba el CTD y PSA en la mallas de las jaulas de salmoneras (**Alejandro Clément, Chile**)

For me Patrick was a pioneer, a firebrand, a mentor, an intellectual, a sometime comedian, a generous spirit and a loveable rogue but mostly he was a friend (**Pauhla McGrane, Ireland**)

Any successful organization needs visionary members who are passionate about the outcome of the mission, and that describes Patrick very well ... A warm, gallant individual with a wicked sense of humor who would not hesitate to express his opinion (**Raphael Kudela, USA**)

Photo Don Anderson

Late night 'discussions' often heated, were always inventive and stimulating. Patrick disliked dogma, courted controversy and made you see the world in a new light (from HABIT website)

His frankness and feed back was refreshing and helpful in handling both science and people issues (**Henrik Enevoldsen, Denmark**)

Su agudeza mental, su claridad, sencillez y serenidad para expresarse, mostrando siempre un rostro generoso, afable y también, por qué no, porque compartíamos el mismo

deseo irrefrenable de fumar (**José Carreto, Argentina**)

He loved the science and he made it fun to talk about. There were always new results, ideas, and connections in his considerations... His leadership of committees and workshops was fundamental, all performed with grace, competence and elegance. But for all his contributions, it is still his presence, twinkling eyes, and sometimes sardonic smile that I miss the most (**Tom Osborn, USA**)

His infectious enthusiasm drove the project [HABIT], and was reflected in his excitement during a chase of a tiny, yet high density, patch of Dinophysis drifting along the Irish coast. He encouraged and was patient with the team of students from Ireland, who on more than one occasion (and not entirely to his displeasure) remarked on his similarity to 007 Sean Connery! (**Robin Raine, Ireland**)

His glasses are slightly lowered on his nose, his head is tilted, and legs are crossed. The ash from his unfiltered cigarette is about to drop to the ground. He smiles with that most pleasant smile that creates a dimple on one side of his face. With a twinkle in his eye and that wonderful French accent, he greets me with his smoky voice ... His support, encouragement and complimentary, friendly demeanor fill me with an understanding of how collaboration forms friendships and how science among friends is one of the best aspects of our jobs (**Vera Trainer, USA**)

... his clear vision and razor-sharp intellect ... He pushed his colleagues to develop unique techniques fit to test clearly formulated scientific hypotheses, such as the sampling of thin layers, and he had inspired a generation of colleagues and students in his area. Patrick was astonishing in his way to go to the end of things (he was working with all his colleagues to the very last day) (**Phil Hess, France**)

Patrick was a great mind, a true researcher, always looking for something new. His fascination for the

interplay between physics and the biota has motivated most of his research, and his contributions to this still developing field are remarkable ... it was with contagious enthusiasm that he showed me his new microlayer sampler ... These memories make me realise that I lost not only an immensely knowledgeable colleague, but also a very good friend (**Maurice Levasseur, Canada**)

... one phrase comes to mind above all others – "scientific rigor". Patrick held himself (and all of us) to very high scientific standards (**Don Anderson, USA**)

Photo Sonsoles González-Gil.

Patrick was an inexhaustible information source, always open for discussions ... Availability and enthusiasm for science well define him (**Laure Guillou, France**)

... in 1997 ... I met Patrick among the other "grandparents" of the discipline ... he added a bit of healthy banter and scientific jousting to the occasion, and perhaps also a bit of smoky French charm (**Martina Doblin, Australia**)

He was one of the coolest people I have had the pleasure of meeting in our field. He was fantastic, a great mind, and taught me so much ... Declan will really miss him too - he loved hanging out with him. They both loved telling stories and having the craic (**Carolina Cusack, Ireland**)

Eutreptiella marina (Euglenophyceae) bloom causes significant fish kills in Banderas Bay, Jalisco, México

Fig. 1. Location of sampling in Banderas Bay, Jalisco México.

Phytoplankton analyses in April 25 and 27, 2009, in the southern part of Banderas Bay (Bahía de Banderas), Jalisco, Mexico (Fig. 1), revealed the presence of a potentially harmful bloom of *Eutreptiella marina*. Samples were stored in a 50 ml plastic bottle, and preserved with Lugol-acetate solution. Phytoplankton abundance was determined by the standard Utermöhl technique [1], and algal quantification was made with 100x magnifications in aliquots of 10 ml using a 1mm² Whipple disc with double cross pattern of 100 µm. Temperature was recorded with HOBO temperature/light data logger and salinity with a salinometer. During the days prior to event, gusty winds occurred, with a temperature

Table 1. Phytoplankton abundance during the bloom in Banderas Bay.

Species	Cells · ml ⁻¹	%
<i>Eutreptiella marina</i>	2208	94.52
<i>Pseudoguinaridia recta</i>	2	0.09
<i>Chaetoceros sp.</i>	4	0.17
<i>Dictyocha californica</i>	48	2.05
<i>Peridinium quinquecorne</i>	8	0.34
<i>Rhizosolenia sp.</i>	2	0.09
<i>Diatomea central N.I. cadena</i>	10	0.43
<i>Diatomea pennada N.I.</i>	2	0.09
<i>Diatomea central N.I.</i>	2	0.09
<i>Proboscia SP.</i>	12	0.51
<i>Thalassiosira sp.</i>	10	0.43
<i>Prorocentrum micans</i>	2	0.09
<i>Prorocentrum gracile</i>	8	0.34
<i>Pseudonitzschia sp.</i>	10	0.43
<i>Ceratium balechii</i>	2	0.09
<i>Ceratium fusus</i>	6	0.26
	2336	100.00

range of 24.5 to 25°C and 35 psu, as well green sea water discoloration, the colour of anti-freeze (Fig. 2); bright plumes were also seen. Hundreds of dead fish were observed on the beach and at the surface of Banderas Bay, possibly due to oxygen depletion following the bloom. On the other hand, Zimba *et al* [4] identified neurotoxin

production by two similar species, *Euglena sanguinea* and *E. granulate*; both species grow well in eutrophic environments. Increased nitrification of wetlands, wastewater treatment systems, and runoff from urbanization, increase suitable habitat for growth of these algae in Banderas Bay, and there has been a rapid shift in phytoplankton community composition. On May 11th the dinoflagellate *Prorocentrum micans* caused an enormous bloom in the vicinity with 10.13×10^6 cells L⁻¹; this abundance has never been recorded before in this area. Two days later, on May 13th, an *Akashiwo sanguina* bloom with densities between 760×10^3 and 566×10^3 cells L⁻¹ replaced the *Prorocentrum micans* population. The

Eutreptiella marina bloom reached a maximum concentration of 2.21×10^6 cells L⁻¹ (Table 1) with 94% dominance, enough to be lethal with a temperature range of 24.5–25 °C and 35 psu (Table 2). These *E. marina* cells are cylindrical to elongate oval, with a variable number of chloroplasts, 15–80 µm long, 3–15 µm wide, and swim rapidly [3], (Fig. 3A–E). According to Bravo [2], *Eutreptiella gimnastica* Schiller (= *E. marina* Cunha, 1914) is the only euglenophyte in Mexican Pacific, which he describes as coastal in polluted areas with high organic contamination, with no outbreaks or associated toxicity. No harmful

Fig. 2. Greenish water in the bloom area of *Eutreptiella marina*.

bloom of *E. marina* has been seen on the Jalisco coast before, and this is the first record for the Mexican coast. No human health effects or intoxication were associated with this event, only hundreds of dead fish (Fig. 4A-B).

The affected fish included balloon fish, Mexican needlefish, snapper, moray, and the Californian salem. Table 3 shows the affected organisms in several localities of Banderas Bay. The salem (*Xenistius californiensis*) were washed ashore in hundreds, and many were also found dead in open waters; this species was the most affected, with specimens 24 to 26 cm long. During the *E. marina* bloom, the sea water was described as unusually turbid, and the heaviest concentration of dead fish were in the southern part of the bay. Fish were also observed gasping at the surface with erratic behaviour; up to 90% had with lesions, bleeding in the internal organs, but with gills, eyes, skin and fins healthy.

Fig. 3. Forms of *Eutreptiella marina*: a) elongated and thin forms; b) showing its two unequal flagella: 1- short, 2- long; c) wide form; d) rounded form; e) drop-shaped

Table 2. Temperature, salinity and deep of sampling stations.

Coordinates		Continental reference	Temp. °C	Salinity psu	Deep (m)
Latitude	Length				
20° 39' 07"	105° 13' 45"	Dársena Portuaria	25	35	11.0
20° 37' 57"	105° 14' 10"	Hotel Sheraton	25	35	36.0
20° 36' 26"	105° 14' 44.7"	Boca de Tomatlán	24.5	35	39.0
20° 31' 00"	105° 16' 05"	Yelapa	24.7	35	40.0

Table 3. Fishes affected by *Eutroptiella marina* bloom in Banderas Bay, Jalisco, México.

	Scientific name	Common name	Abundance
1	<i>Diodon holocantus</i>	Balloon fish	Few
2	<i>Tylosurus crocodilius</i>	Mexican needlefishes	Few
3	Family Haemulidae	Snapper	Few
4	<i>Muraena argus</i>	Moray	Few
5	Family Cupleidae	Pacific sardines	Hundreds
6	<i>Xenistius californiensis</i>	Californian salema	Hundreds

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Fig. 4. a) Fish kill in the greenish water. b) Some fish samples, the reference square is 30 cm per side.

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11th IOC-AECID-IEO Course on HAB Taxonomy

The 11th IOC-AECID-IEO Course on Taxonomy of Harmful Phytoplankton was held in Vigo, Spain, in June 2010. As in previous years, this course was jointly sponsored by the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) of UNESCO, the Spanish Agency for International Cooperation and Development (AECID) and the Spanish Institute of Oceanography (IEO).

The course was intended for Latin-American and African experts with experience in microalgae identification, responsible for setting up or strengthening their national or regional harmful marine microalgae monitoring programmes.

For the second time in Vigo, the course had an e-learning part which participants were to complete before attending the classes held in Vigo.

This e-learning was supported by the IOC Science and Communication

Centre on Harmful Algae in Copenhagen. Jacob Larsen was in charge, and used the Absalon e-learning platform at Copenhagen University. This part of the course comprised approximately 45 hours of individual learning.

The second part of the course was held in Vigo from 2nd to 18th June. It comprised 97 hours of lectures and practical sessions on the identification of harmful algae and cysts, as well as introductory lessons on biotoxins, monitoring and management of harmful events, chemical taxonomy and molecular tools, ecology, and sampling at sea and in the laboratory. Participants were also able to report on their national HAB events, exchanging impressions on their experiences.

14 scientists from Angola, Chile, Colombia, Cuba, Mexico, Peru and Spain attended the course.

This year we had Jacob Larsen and

Celia Villac as guest teachers, as well as our usual “local collaborators” for these courses: Santiago Fraga, Isabel Bravo, Beatriz Reguera, Francisco Rodríguez and Pilar Rial from the IEO, Vigo; José Franco and Pilar Riobó from IIM-CSIC, Vigo; Covadonga Salgado, Yolanda Pazos and Angeles Moroño from INTECMAR; María Rodríguez-Velasco from the EU-CRLMB, Vigo; and Monica Lion from the IOC-IEO SCCHA, Vigo.

Participants contributed actively to the classes and we enjoyed a superb work atmosphere.

If you are interested in this kind of IOC training activities, please check our web site <http://ioc.unesco.org/hab/> for complementary information.

Course photos on page 15.

Dinophysis norvegica: First report of the toxic temperate water *Dinophysis* in Manori creek of Mumbai water

Fig. 1. Manori Creek (MC) of Mumbai coast. The dot at the mouth of creek is the exact location of sampling.

Dinophysis is a group of unicellular microscopic eukaryotic algae. The genus *Dinophysis* is the largest genus under family Dinophysiaceae of order Dinophysiales. Like other dinoflagellate algae, some members of *Dinophysis* contain toxins that get accumulated in bivalve shellfishes, while the later feed on the algae. The toxins cause diarrhea in human who consume the infected shellfishes. The disease outbreak is known as Diarrhetic shellfish poisoning (DSP). Unlike Paralytic shellfish poisoning (PSP), another type of algae-originated poisoning, DSP cases is rarely fatal. DSP outbreaks have long been overlooked because the symptoms DSP are often mistaken for bacteria caused diarrhea [1]. The DSP causing algae have drawn little attention in India, even though they have been reported at a potentially alarming density in Indian waters [2]. We specifically studied this important group of algae in Manori creek of Mumbai water. We are reporting the presence of *Dinophysis norvegica*, a toxic member of *Dinophysis* group, known to be a temperate water species. This assumes significance because there is a possibility of algal species being transferred through ballast water of ships.

The sampling site is located at northern most side of Mumbai in Manori creek (Fig. 1) that opens to Arabian Sea on the west side. Manori creek has a number of *Meretrix meretrix* beds

contributing to seasonal fishery all throughout the year, except during monsoon. There are few beach resorts, salt pans and water recreational activities along the creek. The bottom is muddy with high organic load. This creek is also a ferry site and has rich mangrove vegetation (*Avicennia marina*).

Monthly sampling was done at the mouth of Manori Creek from June 2005 to May 2006 during high tide for qualitative and quantitative analysis of *Dinophysis*. Sampling was not done in August due to rough weather and heavy rain.

The phytoplankton samples were collected by filtering 20 L of surface water with plankton net of 10 mm mesh size. The filtrates (50 ml) were then passed through 200 mm net to remove large zooplanktons. The plankton concentrates were fixed immediately with lugols iodine [3] as well as with formaldehyde. Live samples were also collected by similar means, but brought to the laboratory without fixing. The observations were made within 2 hours of collection. Sea surface and atmospheric temperatures were recorded in the field using mercury thermometer. Water samples fixed with Winkler's solution were brought to lab for Dissolved Oxygen (DO) analysis. Water samples were also collected in glass bottle for nutrients analysis. Other water quality parameters like pH, salinity and Biological Oxygen Demand (BOD) were estimated in laboratory. Phytoplanktons were identified by their morphology, cell size and thecal plate patterns, using inverted epifluorescence microscope. Cells were counted by loading 1 ml of iodine fixed sample in Gridded Sedgwick Rafter Slide (wild life supply company, USA). A total 300 chambers were counted for enumerating the plankton number.

During the study period, seventeen samplings were done. Total plankton count, total dinoflagellate count and count of *Dinophysis* were done during the analysis. Though dinoflagellates like *Alexandrium* spp and *Gymnodinium*

spp were present in almost all the samples, *Dinophysis* groups were present only in few samples. Among *Dinophysis* members *D. caudata*, *D. norvegica*, *D. dens*, *D. rotundata* and *D. aciminata* were observed sporadically at low cell concentrations [4]. Among all the *Dinophysis* species recorded, *D. norvegica* drew our attention because it is a bloom-forming toxic species associated with DSP events and is widely distributed in cold to temperate coastal waters of the Northern Hemisphere [5]. *D. norvegica* is the producer of dinophysistoxin-1 and okadaic acid, the two toxins implicated in DSP cases. DSP is not fatal but may cause stomach tumor on prolonged exposure [6].

Out of seventeen samples collected, *D. norvegica* was present only in three samples. *D. norvegica* was identified by morphology of the left sulcal list & the ribs supporting it, shape & size of the cingular lists and the size of epicone. The morphological characteristic of this species (Fig. 2) matched completely with the description of Dodge [7] and Tomas [8].

The cell concentration of *D. norvegica* was 114 cells L⁻¹ on 18th July 2005, 46 cells L⁻¹ on 30th November 2005 and 81 cells L⁻¹ on 8 December 2005. Though another member of the same genus, *Dinophysis fortii*, has been reported to cause poisoning at a concentration of 200 cells L⁻¹ [9], the concentrations with respect to *D. norvegica* has been in the order of 0.5×10^6 when associated with

Fig. 2. *Dinophysis norvegica*. Scale bar = 10 μ m (lateral view).

Table 1. Nutrients concentration in surface water at the time of presence of *D. norvegica*.

Date	Sea surface Temperature (°C)	Salinity (PSU)	Dissolved Oxygen (mg L ⁻¹)	Biological oxygen demand (mg L ⁻¹)	NH ₄ -N (µg L ⁻¹)	NO ₃ -N (µg L ⁻¹)	NO ₂ -N (µg L ⁻¹)	PO ₄ -P (µg L ⁻¹)
18/7/2005	32.0	23	4.9±0.2	3.80±0.49	15.7±4.6	27.6±5.1	108.7±7.1	155.4±37.4
30/11/2005	26.0	36.0	7.8±1.67	13.4±1.1	52.3±6.1	33.7±7.0	126.6.0±4.1	240.5±59.9
8/12/2005	25.0	34.5	0.44±0.17	8.15±0.85	45±3.9	19.3±4.0	149.4±5.2	169.4±18.2

outbreaks [10]. Therefore, the concentrations recorded in Mumbai water are not very alarming. Moreover, the minuscule proportion of the total phytoplankton *D. norvegica* constituted does not indicate a blooming situation.

Interestingly, being a temperate water species, *D. norvegica* was recorded over a wide range of temperature and salinity. The average surface water temperature ranged between 25°C–32°C, while salinity ranged between 23–36 PSU on the sampling days, when it was recorded. The DO ranged between 0.44 ± 0.17 mg L⁻¹ to 7.8 ± 1.67 mg L⁻¹ and BOD between 3.8 ± 0.49 to 13.4 ± 1.1 mg L⁻¹. BOD values were found to be high indicating high organic pollutant in water. Concentration of different nutrients on the days when *D. norvegica* was recorded is given (Table 1). As stated, *D. norvegica* was recorded in July, November and December. The physico-chemical parameters are expected to change significantly over this time period. Understandably, the density of cells of *D. norvegica* did not correlate with any of the environmental as well as hydrological parameters. To our knowledge *D. norvegica* is not reported from Mumbai waters of India.

Presence of this temperate water toxic species in tropical climate proves

the theory of aggravation of HAB events by ballast water and ocean currents. Since Mumbai has a major port, there is a possibility that this species might have entered by ballast water discharge. It is now commonly accepted that ships while taking and discharging ballast water can cause transfer of planktonic organisms between different geographical areas. Though it is hard for a temperate water species to survive and establish in a new environment, presence of *D. norvegica* in July as well as November and December indicate that the survivability is probably not temporary. Even though, their number is very less, we need to take it as a signal that under favorable environmental conditions it has potential to cause bloom and human intoxication.

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Snapshots from the 11th IOC-AECID-IEO Course.
See page 13.

Green discolorations in Nuevo Gulf, Chubut Province, Argentina

Fig. 1. Green blooms cover large part of Golfo Nuevo. Southern Right Whales are observed.

Intense green discolorations were produced in the waters of Nuevo Gulf in the spring of 2007 and 2008 (Fig. 1). The appearance of these large green blooms in the Gulf coincided with an apparent increase in mortality of the Southern Right Whale (*Eubalaena australis*), particularly among calves [1–2]. This species of dinoflagellate has been observed along our coasts since 1998, with increased abundance in the last two years. The aim of this study was to identify the organism producing these algal blooms and analyze the potential production of toxins.

Península Valdés (between 42°S and 43°S) is situated on the Atlantic coast of Patagonia where the San Matías, San José and Nuevo Gulfs coincide. These bodies of water are commonly referred to as the North Patagonian Gulfs (Fig. 2). Nuevo Gulf (from 42° 29' S to 43° S and 65° 03' to 64° 03' W) is a semi-closed ecosystem limited by a mouth of 12 km which minimizes water exchange with the open sea [3]. This Gulf has an area of approximately 2,200 km² and average

depth of 90 m and maximum of 170 m. Nueva Bay is situated to the extreme west of Nuevo Gulf (42° 45' S and 65° 02' W) and is characterized by a semi-open morphology, with an approximate surface area of 5.8 km² and volume of 1.1 km³. Scarce information on current velocity in the interior of the bay suggests extremely weak flow (~2.5 cm seg⁻¹) [4]. Puerto Madryn city is the only urban development located in front of the Bay.

Live samples of the green algal bloom were taken from Nueva Bay and were observed under an optic microscope both with and without phase contrast. Photomicrographs of the observed phytoplankton cells were taken and the cells were measured. Quantitative analyses were carried out using an inverted microscope following Utermöhl's technique.

Microscopic observations showed both algal blooms were produced by a small dinoflagellate gimnodinioide with green chloroplasts accumulated on its surface (Fig. 3). The dinoflagellate was identified as *Lepidodinium* sp., whose morphological characteristics include: Subglobular cell, slightly dorsoventrally compressed; Length: 20–25 µm; Width: 10–12.5 µm; Subconic episoma equal or slightly shorter than the hiposoma; Cingulum descendent and slightly displaced.

The dinoflagellates observed under the light of the microscope were shown to quickly lose shape, secrete mucilage and aggregate together forming cell

Fig. 3. Living cell of *Lepidodinium* sp.

masses (Fig. 4).

Claquin *et al.* [5] has shown that this species produces ten times more transparent exopolymeric particles (TEP), compared with seven other species of cultured microalgae.

Richter *et al.* [6] studied the vertical diurnal migration of *L. chlorophorum* in the water column and the impact of solar radiation on its motility. They found that solar radiation resulted in a slight but significant decrease in swim velocity and in percentage of mobil cells after five hours of exposure to all radiation treatments. However, although cells were distributed more or less homogeneously throughout the water column, a slight but significant response was observed at midday when cells migrated to deeper parts of the water column to avoid high radiation.

Observations under the optic microscope were unable to distinguish between *Lepidodinium chlorophorum*

(= *Gymnodinium chlorophorum*) [7–8] and *L. viride* [9], whose defining characteristics can only be observed with an electron microscope. These two species contain both chlorophyll *a* and chlorophyll *b*, uncommon pigment in dinoflagellates. These species are also characterized as the only organisms possessing an

Fig. 2. Location of North Patagonian Gulfs

vestigial eukaryotic endosymbiont of prasinophytic lineage [7, 9–10].

MODIS Aqua satellite images taken from September 30 to October 7, 2007, show high values of chlorophyll in the entire Nuevo Gulf region (more than 30 mg/m³) (Fig. 5). However, quantitative analysis of phytoplankton samples of two coastal stations, Folías and Punta Pardelas, observed 5,080 cells/L (12% total phytoplankton) and 61,448 cells/L (51% total phytoplankton) for the same time period. In October 2008, during the second discoloration event, Punta Pardelas station registered 53,760 cells/L (26% total phytoplankton).

Neither of these values are representative of a phytoplanktonic bloom. Thus, it can be inferred that the bloom did not reach coastal areas.

Similar green dinoflagellate blooms have been observed in other seas around the world, such as the Adriatic Sea [11], the North Sea [7] and western coasts of France [12] and Spain [13].

Chromophotographic analysis of paralyzing toxins carried out by the Laboratory of Chromotography of the Department of Environmental Health, Chubut Province, showed negative results coinciding with results found in other seas, thus ruling out its presence as cause for whale mortality (G. Marino, pers. comm.). However, *L. chlorophorum* is cited as a harmful species that causes anoxia, endangers marine life (especially sedentary species) and obstructs fish gills [14–15].

Fig. 5. MODIS Aqua satellite image showing chlorophyll concentration

Fig. 4. a, b, c and d: The dinoflagellate showing different cellular shapes.

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The GEOHAB Core Research Project on HABs in Fjords & Coastal Embayments launches its research plan

This recently published research plan summarizes the Open Science Meeting (OSM) held in Chile in April 2004 and provides the proceedings, progress and synthesis of research efforts on the study of HABs in fjords and other coastal embayments. This report also discusses a wide variety of research topics related to HABs in these coastal systems, and identifies key research questions. These include the influence of embayment morphology, bathymetry and hydrodynamics on HAB dynamics, particular adaptive strategies of harmful algae in these systems, the importance of life history transitions and cyst distribution, the role of physical aggregation and dispersion mechanisms, the relative contribution of nutrient flux and supply ratios, the importance of spatial scale and retention time in the expression and effects of allelochemicals and toxins in semi-

confined systems, and the influence of anthropogenic activities such as aquaculture and climate change on HAB dynamics. Our understanding of and ability to predict HABs in coastal embayments over the next 5-10 years will reflect the extent to which this GEOHAB CRP can answer these questions. The practical implementation of Core Research activities in coastal embayments was initiated in 2005. A sub-committee for this CRP was formed recently; it includes Drs Allan Cembella (Germany), Leonardo Guzmán (Chile), Marina Montresor (Italy) and Suzanne Roy (Canada). An Open Science Meeting is planned for 2011, focusing on life history transitions, particularly the connection between benthic cysts and blooms in coastal embayments.

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More info at: www.geohab.info

A Regional Plan for HAB Research Focus and Cooperation in Asia

Many countries in Asia face problems associated with harmful algal blooms, especially those that border the China Sea and western Pacific. Blooms are formed by toxic species that cause human intoxications, kill wild and cultured fishes, and others that are noxious but non toxic. In some areas noxious blooms are also formed by

macroalgae. Several of the HAB species affect more than one country in the region. These include *Pyrodinium bahamense*, *Alexandrium* spp., *Cochlodinium polykrikoides*, *Noctiluca scintillans*, and *Phaeocystis globosa*. Early on, many researchers in Asia realized the value of establishing cooperative and comparative studies on HABs in the region based upon the GEOHAB model. This approach would harmonize research plans and methods, facilitate exchange of information and expertise, and provide access to technologies that may not be available in some countries.

In order to produce a science plan for GEOHAB Asia, two meetings were convened. During the first meeting on 15-16 March 2007 held in Tokyo Japan participants presented HAB-related research carried out in their respective countries. In the second meeting from 31 Jan to 1 Feb 2008 held in Nha Trang Vietnam the presentations were more focused on identifying key questions and research components to be included in

the GEOHAB Asia science plan. The meetings were also attended by some members of the GEOHAB Scientific Steering Committee, representatives from the North Pacific Marine Sciences Organization (PICES), and some prominent HAB scientists from outside Asia. The output of these meetings is a research plan entitled "Harmful Algal Blooms in Asia: A Regional Comparative Programme". The plan is available for perusal and download from the GEOHAB homepage. It is hoped that starting in 2011 some studies outlined in the research plan will be implemented by researchers in the region. Success of the two planning meetings was facilitated by generous support of the Japanese government, the Danish International Development Agency (DANIDA) and IOC/WESTPAC.

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The GEOHAB Core Research Project on Benthic HABs is launched

Ciguatera is caused by a type of dinoflagellate (*Gambierdiscus spp.*) that grows epiphytically on macroalgae in coral reef environments. These and other dinoflagellates such as *Ostreopsis*, *Prorocentrum*, and *Coolia* are consumed by herbivorous fish, beginning processes of bioaccumulation through the food web as herbivorous fish are consumed by carnivores and ultimately by humans. Collectively such organisms may be referred to as Benthic Harmful Algal Blooms (BHABs). Because of their significant threat to human health, fisheries resources, and marine ecosystems, attention has been focused on international coordination of research on BHABs. The importance of such toxin-producing, benthic organisms throughout tropical areas worldwide led the Scientific Steering Committee of the Global Ecology and Oceanography of Harmful Algal

Blooms (GEOHAB) program to create a Core Research Project (CRP) for BHABs. GEOHAB is co-sponsored by the Scientific Committee on Oceanic Research (SCOR) and the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) of the United Nations Education, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO). Establishment of a CRP begins with an open science meeting to bring together the international science communities studying these organisms to create structure for future research collaborations.

Recently an open science meeting for BHABs was organized and convened in Honolulu, Hawaii, USA. This meeting attracted an international group of over sixty scientists from more than twenty countries to share their insights regarding BHABs in various environments. An

accompanying training workshop for twenty researchers was designed to harmonize protocols for sampling and taxonomic identification of BHABs to be applied by researchers throughout the world. Subsequent to these activities, the organizing committee for the meeting is leading the production of a conceptual research plan to provide the foundation for collaborative research on oceanographic and ecologic controls on BHAB species to be presented at the 14th International Conference of Harmful Algae in Crete later this year. *Gambierdiscus spp.* are responsible for more human illness than all other HAB-species combined, and it is important to have assembled the international communities studying these organisms to erect an international structure for future research collaborations in comparable systems.

GEOHAB Training Workshop: Taxonomy challenges and identification of benthic dinoflagellates

In conjunction with the GEOHAB Open Science Meeting on Benthic HABs held 21-23 June 2010, Hawaii, USA, was held a training workshop from 24 to 27 June on 'Taxonomy challenges and identification of benthic dinoflagellates'. The training workshop included microscopy and molecular techniques and trainers included Drs. Jacob Larsen, Wayne Litaker, Pat Tester and Mona Hoppenrath. Local microscope distributor PAC/RIM

Medical Technology & Supplies Corp. provided the microscopes. Participants worked with both samples from cultures

and the field that had been identified. Known species could be compared with the drawings and micrographs and it was

Photo by N.N. Lam

a good mix of fresh samples from Hawaii, known species samples from around the world and the samples the participants had brought with them for examination/identification. As always training workshops provide the opportunity to network and build relationships and not the least for taxonomists, who are often not well supported, this is also a major outcome of a workshop.

Future events

SEPTEMBER 2010

Oceanography and ecology of HABs: physical/biological interactions

Nantes, France, 20–24 Sep

Session at the ICES Annual Science Conference 2010.

More info at: www.ices.dk/iceswork/asc/2010

AOAC Annual Meeting

Orlando, Florida, 26–29 Sep

There will be a Marine and Freshwater Toxins Taskforce meeting and also the following symposia:

- Marine toxin control – Modern methods, validations, animal use reduction, and international standards.
- Issues and criteria for validation of analytical methods for cyanotoxins detection and global suitability.
- Natural toxins impact and methods needs in the developing world.

For further info visit: www.aoac.org/meetings1/124th_annual_mtg/main_2.htm, or contact J. Hungerford (James.Hungerford@fda.hhs.gov).

NOVEMBER 2010

Taxonomy of Recent Dinophyceae by Malte Elbrächter

List/Sylt, Germany, 2–8 Nov

The course, that will be held at the Wattenmeerstation Sylt of the Alfred Wegener Institut für Polar- und Meeresforschung.

Registration deadline: 15 Aug

Registration: Malte.Elbraechter@awi.de

More info at: www.ioc-unesco.org/hab/index.php?option=com_oe&task=viewDoclistRecord&doclistID=71

Baltic Sea Phytoplankton Species Identification Course

Tvärminne, Hanko, Finland, 14–26 Nov

Nordic Marine Academy Awarded this course that will be held in Tvärminne Zoological Station.

Teaching by Ø. Moestrup, H. Kuosa, S. Hällfors, J. Larsen, A. Kremp, H. Annadotter, H. Hällfors, M. Majaneva, J. Blomster and J-M. Rintala.

The course corresponds to 5 ECTS-credits and it is primarily meant for researchers/students at the Postdoctoral and Ph.D.-level with previous experience in Baltic Sea phytoplankton identification.

Participants should be actively working on different aspects of phytoplankton ecology, physiology and/or taxonomy.

Application deadline: 31 Aug.

For additional info contact: J.-M. Rintala (janne.rintala@helsinki.fi).

JANUARY 2011

Aspen Ocean Symposium: Physical microenvironments modulating biological interactions in the Ocean

Aspen, Colorado, USA, 17–21 Jan

The meeting will address how physical microenvironments affect marine organisms, focusing on seven 'microscale' themes bringing together biologists, chemists, ecologists, physicists, engineers, and mathematicians for a highly interactive workshop. A mixture of invited talks, contributed short talks, posters and discussion sessions, as well as ample time for informal interactions, will foster novel views and collaborations at the interface between physics, biology and chemistry.

For more info: web.mit.edu/aspenoceansymp

APRIL 2011

IPHAB-X: Tenth Session of the IOC Intergovernmental Panel on Harmful Algal Blooms

Paris, France, 12–14 Apr (tentative dates)

Session will be held at UNESCO Headquarters.

More info at: www.ioc-unesco.org/hab

JUNE 2011

8th International Conference on Molluscan Shellfish Safety (ICMSS)

Charlottetown, Prince Edward Island, Canada, 12–17 Jun

The Canadian Food Inspection Agency and the Prince Edward Island Department of Fisheries, Aquaculture and Rural Development are pleased to announce that the 8th ICMSS will be held at the University of Prince Edward Island located in Charlottetown.

Scientists from all over the world will gather in Charlottetown to discuss issues such as microbiology, chemistry and marine biotoxin risks, analytical methods, molluscan shellfish harvest area management and more.

The conference will provide the international community an excellent forum to advance molluscan shellfish safety science and advocate the soundness in its application. It also provides a good opportunity for the science and academic community, industry participants and regulators to establish and maintain contacts around the globe.

More info can be found at: www.gov.pe.ca/ICMSS2011

See you in Hersonissos, Crete, in November!

HARMFUL ALGAE NEWS

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